

Oxidation of benzyl ethers by *N*-bromosuccinimide : A kinetic and mechanistic study

N. Mathiyalagan* and R. Sridharan

Postgraduate and Research Department of Chemistry, St. Joseph's College, Tiruchirappalli-620 002, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : sjcmathi@yahoo.co.uk sridharannr@sify.com

Manuscript received 30 May 2005, revised 25 October 2005, accepted 19 January 2006

Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of benzyl ethers by *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in 80% aqueous acetic acid has been investigated. The reaction follows first-order kinetics with respect to both [NBS] and [substrate]. The effects of varying ionic strength and dielectric constant indicate the reaction is a dipole-dipole type. Addition of succinimide (>NH), has a negligible effect on the rate of oxidation. The product of oxidation is benzaldehyde. From the effect of temperature on the reaction rate, the Arrhenius and the activation parameters have been calculated. A suitable mechanism has been proposed and a rate law explaining the experimental results is derived.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, benzyl ethers, *N*-bromosuccinimide.

N-Halogeno compounds are known to be versatile oxidizing agent¹. Kinetic investigations involving esters², aldoses³, alcohols⁴, ketones^{5,6}, aldehydes^{7,8}, amino acids^{9,10}, thiocyanate ion¹¹ and thiosemicarbazide¹² with NBS as oxidizing agent have been reported. However, the kinetics of oxidation of benzyl ethers viz. benzyl methyl ether, benzyl propyl ether and benzyl isobutyl ether by NBS has not been reported so far and hence need for the title investigation.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of benzyl ethers by NBS is investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants. Under the condition [NBS] \ll [benzyl ether] the oxidation of benzyl ether by NBS proceeds smoothly at 40 °C in aqueous acetic acid medium. The plot of log [NBS] vs time is linear up to 65% of the reaction and the rate constant is reproducible with $\pm 3\%$, showing a first-order dependence on [NBS]¹³.

Effect of [benzyl ether] is carried out at different initial concentrations of benzyl ether, keeping other parameters constant (Table 1). The plot of log k_{obs} vs log [benzyl ether] is also linear ($r = 0.996$) with unit slope showing first-order dependence on [benzyl ether].

The reaction is conducted at different ionic strength using NaClO₄ and keeping the concentration of other reactants constant. Increasing ionic strength of the medium

Table 1. Effect of concentration of benzyl ether on the reaction rate at 323 K

[NBS] = 2×10^{-3} M, [NaClO₄] = 0.2 M, solvent = 80% AcOH - 20% H₂O (v/v)

[Benzyl ether] $\times 10^2$ M	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹		
	Benzyl methyl ether	Benzyl propyl ether	Benzyl isobutyl ether
2.0	1.66	2.37	2.51
2.5	2.04	2.98	3.15
3.0	2.48	3.63	3.85
3.5	2.91	4.18	4.46
4.0	3.34	4.78	5.10
4.5	3.90	5.28	5.70
5.0	4.50	5.84	6.35
5.5	4.70	6.49	6.98
6.0	4.96	7.20	7.67
6.5	5.40	7.68	8.21
7.0	5.88	8.30	8.80

increases the rate (Table 2). The plot of log k_{obs} vs μ is linear ($r = 0.989$) with positive slope, indicates that the reaction is between two-dipoles.

In order to determine the rate dependence on solvent composition, kinetics are followed in glacial acetic acid-water mixtures in which ratio of water to acetic acid is

Table 2. Effect of varying $[\text{NaClO}_4]$ on the reaction rate at 323 K
 $[\text{NBS}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{benzyl ether}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 solvent = 80% AcOH - 20% H_2O (v/v)

$[\text{NaClO}_4]$	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$		
	Benzyl methyl ether	Benzyl propyl ether	Benzyl isobutyl ether
<i>M</i>	ether	ether	ether
0.0	1.10	1.71	1.85
0.1	1.40	2.11	2.25
0.2	1.66	2.37	2.51
0.3	1.91	2.62	2.76

varied. It is observed that an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate constant (Table 3). Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ (D is dielectric constant of the medium) is linear ($r = 0.929$) with negative slope, indicating the reaction is a dipole-dipole type¹³.

Effect of added succinimide ($>\text{NH}$) is studied at different initial concentration of succinimide. It has negligible effect on the rate of oxidation. The reaction mixture fails to initiate polymerization of aqueous acrylamide solution, indicating the absence of free radicals.

The oxidation of benzyl ether has been studied at different temperature (313–328 K), the Arrhenius and the activation parameters are evaluated (Table 4).

Mechanism :

Under the experimental condition studied, the possible oxidizing species are Br^+ , HOBr , NBS and NBSH^+ in aqueous solution. Since the order with respect to NBS is unity, the possible oxidizing species in the present investigation may be NBS itself. NBS itself as an oxidizing species in acetic acid medium has been reported by many authors^{5,9,14}. Assuming NBS as the oxidizing species, the following mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of benzyl ether by NBS .

Table 3. Effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate at 323 K
 $[\text{NBS}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{benzyl ether}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ M}$

$\text{CH}_3\text{COOH-H}_2\text{O}$	<i>D</i>	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$		
		Benzyl methyl ether	Benzyl propyl ether	Benzyl isobutyl ether
% (v/v)		ether	ether	ether
100-0	6.15	0.89	1.60	1.74
80-20	18.00	1.66	2.37	2.51
70-30	24.75	2.02	2.73	2.87
60-40	31.50	2.39	3.10	3.24

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{NBS}] [\text{Benzyl ether}]$$

In this mechanism the positive part of oxidizing species viz. bromine attacks the lone pair of oxygen of the ether in rate determining step. A similar mechanism has also been observed for the oxidation of benzyl ether¹⁵ and alcohols¹⁶. The above mechanism also explains the first-order with respect to NBS and benzyl ether. The increase of rate by increase of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium explain the reaction between two-dipoles in rate determining step. The negative value of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) indicates that the activated complex is cyclic in nature^{3,9,17}. The activation enthalpies and entropies of oxidation of all benzyl ethers are linearly related ($r = 0.999$), implying that all the benzyl ethers undergo oxidation by same mechanism.

Order of reactivity and isokinetic relationship :

The rates of the oxidation of five aliphatic alcohols correlate very well with Taft's σ^* substituent constants¹⁸ with negative value reaction constant. The values of ρ^* at 313, 318 and 323 K are -2.65 ($r = 0.990$), -1.91 ($r = 0.989$) and -1.35 ($r = 0.996$) respectively. This indicates that the transition state of the reaction is positively charged.

Table 4. Effect of temperature on rate and activation parameters for the oxidation of benzyl ethers by NBS at 323 K[NBS] = 2×10^{-3} M, [benzyl ether] = 2×10^{-2} M, [NaClO₄] = 0.2 M, solvent = 80% AcOH – 20% H₂O (v/v)

Benzyl ethers	$10^2 \times k_2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$				E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	313 K	318 K	323 K	328 K				
Benzyl methyl ether	0.41	0.60	0.83	1.13	11.77	9.16	47.88	-123.68
Benzyl propyl ether	0.76	0.95	1.18	1.49	9.23	6.62	45.73	-124.98
Benzyl isobutyl ether	0.87	1.06	1.25	1.77	8.45	5.84	43.13	-125.52

The negative value of polar constant ρ^* indicates that electron donating centers increase the rate of reaction. The order of reactivity among the alcohols is benzyl isobutyl ether > benzyl propyl ether > benzyl methyl ether. It is seen from Table 4 that the activation energy is the highest for slowest reaction.

The genuine nature of isokinetic relationship was verified by the Exner^{19,20} criterion, by plotting $\log k_2$ at 323 K vs $\log k_2$ at 313 K. This plot is found to be linear with ($r = 0.994$) slope (b) equal to 0.54. This linearity of Exner plot is suggestive of unified mechanism for the NBS oxidation of all the three benzyl ethers. From the slope of Exner plot isokinetic temperature (β) is calculated using following equation²¹.

$$\beta = \frac{T_1 T_2 (b - 1)}{b T_2 - T_1}$$

The slope (b) is less than 1 and β (335 K) is greater than T_1 . These results indicate an decreasing selectivity with the increase in temperature and the reaction series is characterized by compensation effect between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger .

Experimental

Materials :

The benzyl ethers (AnalaR, B.D.H.) were used as such without further purification. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (Fluka) was used and its solution was always prepared fresh and its strength was checked by iodometric²² method. Sodium perchlorate used was of AnalaR grade. Triply distilled water was used throughout the course of investigation. Glacial acetic acid (A.R. Qualigen) was purified²³ and 80% of acetic acid 20% water mixture was used.

Kinetic measurements :

The kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo first-order conditions ([benzyl ether] \gg [NBS]). All solutions were thermo-stated for 30 min before mixing. Requisite amounts of benzyl ether, sodium perchlorate and

aqueous acetic acid were taken in jena glass reaction vessel and placed in a water thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. Reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of NBS solution and its progress was followed by estimating iodometrically the amount of unconsumed NBS at regular intervals of time.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The reaction mixture containing excess of NBS over benzyl ethers in presence of NaClO₄ was kept at 40 °C for 48 h. Estimation of unreacted NBS showed that one mole of benzyl ether reacted with one mole of NBS. The products are the corresponding benzaldehyde and alkyl halide.

A mixer of benzyl ether and NBS (3 : 1) was prepared in 80% aqueous acetic acid mixture. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 h. The acetic acid was neutralised with solid sodium carbonate. The products were separated by repeated extraction with ether and identified as benzaldehyde and alkyl halide by TLC and GLC techniques.

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